

FRUIT DRYING METHODS AND THEIR USEFUL FEATURES

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Abstract This article provides information on the methods of drying fruits and their useful properties. The main stages of fruit drying are covered.

Key words: drying, fruit, moisture, substance, enterprise, vegetable, product, process, production, field, preparation, storage.

Introduction

In the gardens and fields of our country, the period of peak ripening corresponds to the summer season. In the summer season, the fruits ripen one after another. Collecting this ripening crop without destroying it requires great responsibility from our entrepreneurs. Peaches, plums and grape varieties that ripen in summer cannot be stored for long. That is why the fruits that are overused are dried. They are dried in the open air, in the sunlight, in special areas on wooden trays, and a medium-quality product is obtained. If they are dried in cool areas or in special dryers, the quality of the fruits will be much higher. Drying is implemented on the basis of priority in the agricultural sector. In the country's agrarian network, there is a huge untapped potential for growing fruit and vegetable products and exporting them.

Materials and methods

Drying means removing moisture from fresh fruits under the influence of high temperature and thereby accumulating dry substances in their tissue cells. Cooperation processes of agricultural enterprises in the sale of fruit and vegetable products in general with enterprises of the service branch of the agricultural

production sector (services related to the preparation, storage and delivery of the product to the consumer) or mutual interest in the direction of a single goal of a large number of fruit and vegetable growers and can be viewed as a process of free association. In recent years, the construction of fruit and vegetable drying plants equipped with the latest technologies has been rampant. They are being built in regions and districts where fruits and vegetables are grown for industrial use. Fruit drying consists of the following main stages: sorting of raw materials according to their quality and size, washing, cleaning, blanching, drying, cooling, homogenizing the moisture content, sorting the finished product into varieties and cleaning it from foreign impurities, packing and storage.

After drying, the raw material should have the color, aroma, taste and shape characteristic of this variety, as well as be perishable and conform to the quality standard. Raw materials are washed after being separated into varieties, during washing they are cleaned of impurities and husks, wax. Washed fruits are trimmed if necessary, trimming can be done before or after blanching. Apples are rounded, pears are sliced, peaches and apricots are cut in half. Berries and small-grained fruits, plums are often dried whole without trimming the apricots.

If the fruits are cut into pieces, they dry quickly. It is also necessary to prepare products for culinary processing. Blanching consists of immersing fresh fruit in boiling water or spraying with steam; in this, the vital activity of enzymes, mainly oxidizing enzymes, stops. In addition, since the insoluble pectin substance becomes soluble, the texture of the raw material becomes porous. All this helps to preserve the normal color of raw materials during drying and rapid evaporation of water. If the raw material is blanched after shearing, beneficial soluble substances are partially lost, therefore, it is often blanched whole without shearing.

To preserve the natural color of some fruits, they are dusted with sulfur gas before drying. Fruits can be dried in specially equipped dryers, as well as in direct sunlight. Drying in sunlight is carried out in places where the air is dry, humidity is low, and the temperature is not lower than 30-35 degrees.

In some regions, fruits are dried both artificially and in sunlight, first the product is partially dried in sunlight, and then it is completely dried in dryers. Apples, pears, grapes, apricots and cherries are spread out in large numbers in the sun-dried fruit and vegetable fields. Raw materials prepared for drying are dried in sunlight. then patnus and galvirs are gathered together and dried completely in the wind.

If the fruits are dried only in sunlight, a thin skin may form on the skin of the fruit, and this skin prevents uniform moisture formation in the product. Evaporation of water is the most important process in drying technology. The temperature of the dried fruit from the dryer varies. To equalize their temperature, the dried product is left in the open air for several hours. If the dried fruits are placed in containers without equalizing the temperature, they may darken quickly during storage. After equalizing the temperature, the product is again divided into varieties. During this work, defective products and various impurities are picked, after which dried fruits and vegetables are put into containers. Products are briquetted in hydraulic presses, which saves containers, and also facilitates the transportation, storage and sale of dried products. Dried fruits and vegetables in briquettes do not mold and are not mechanically damaged.

Currently, due to the development of technologies, it is introduced to dry the fruits until 3-5% moisture content remains, and then to place them in hermetically sealed containers. If moisture is reduced, the volume of the product will decrease and the shelf life will be almost doubled. In addition to drying in the sun and heat dryers, new technology sublimation drying methods have also been developed. This method consists in the fact that the fruits are first placed in vacuums, frozen, and moisture is removed, and fully dried by increasing the temperature in the same apparatus.

After drying, fruits and vegetables are placed in soft and hard containers for storage. Fruits and vegetables that are not mechanically damaged during transportation are placed in soft containers. Dried products should be stored at a

temperature not higher than 20 degrees and 70% air humidity, as well as in a dark place. Warehouses must be prepared for storage in advance. In this case, the inside of the warehouse should be neat, well ventilated, disinfected, and fumigated with sulfur. The floor, walls and ceiling of the warehouse are made of 5 percent copper, and the walls should be white. Inside it should be installed a fan, thermometers and psychrometers, trowse, lamps for lighting and returnable boxes. It needs to be protected from sunlight. Before placing the product, the warehouse is fumigated with sulfur gas, after 2 days the room is ventilated.

Although dried fruits contain little water, they freeze at a low temperature, as a result of which their quality decreases. The most convenient storage temperature is 0-10 degrees. Air humidity is of great importance during the storage of dried products; if the air humidity is high, dried fruits and vegetables absorb moisture, as a result of which mold develops, fermentation processes occur, and many volatile acids are formed. In addition, wet products are damaged by pests. When storing dried fruit products, it is necessary to regularly change the air in the room so that the product does not have foreign odors. Dried fruit products placed in non-hermetic containers can be stored for 1.5-2 years.

Conclusion

Many people prefer dried fruits instead of sweets because dried fruits contain the same nutrients as fresh or frozen fruits. In fact, dried fruit actually retains more vitamins and minerals than fruit bought at the counter or frozen. There is a lot of information about the benefits of dried fruits, but many do not want to believe that they also have harmful sides. Are dried fruits really harmful? The downside is that they are very high in sugar and calories. Therefore, they should be consumed in moderation. Naturally, dried fruits are good for our health, because the non-harmfulness of dried fruits depends on their quality, not their quantity. According to nutritionist scientists of the USA, dried fruits can replace wet fruits. Because dried fruits can be found at any time of the year. When eating

dried fruits, it is necessary to strictly follow the recommendations of nutritionists. Only then will it benefit, not harm.

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